

CONNOTATIVE CONCEPTUALIZATION OF POLYSEMY

Nigora Sobir qizi Jumaboyeva

Samarkand state institute of foreign languages

2nd course student of Master degree

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7597803>

Abstract. this article reveals the connotative conceptualization of polysemous words in which many scientists give their vision and opinion about this fact. In addition, the meanings of connotation, conceptualization and polysemy are given.

Keywords: pure, extralinguistic content, cognitive structures, cognitive paradigm, syntagmatically, paradigmatically, seme , polysemous words.

Many linguists who have been engaged in lexicology, semantics, lexicography, have paid attention to the fact that, with the broadest consideration, the words of each particular language form, as it were, a single system or a number of interrelated subsystems. In a general form, this idea was expressed as follows by L. V. Shcherba: "Words ... serving for mutual understanding of members of a certain collective, form a single complex "fabric", a single system, which, unfortunately, is usually very poorly reflected, or even not reflected at all in existing dictionaries" [1].

The problem of a more complete description of the semantics of a word has attracted the attention of linguists for more than a decade. The dispute between representatives of the concepts of narrow and broad semantics continues. The former insist that the meaning of a word can and should be considered within the framework of linguistics proper. At the same time, significant restrictions are imposed on the object of research. Trying not to leave the limits of "pure" linguistics, linguists who stand in this position proceed from the fact that a person uses only his own to transmit and understand information knowledge of the language and does not refer to other types of knowledge: to information about the author or addressee of the message, about the details of the specific situation in which words are used, to encyclopedic information about the subjects and events in question [2]. The field of semantics in a broad sense refers to all the information that the speaker has in mind when deploying the utterance and which must be restored to the listener for the correct interpretation of the utterance [3].

The traditional, narrow view of semantics does not allow us to take into account all the nuances associated with the meaning of a word, which should be interpreted as broadly as possible – as all the content that consists in a verbal sign. Even A. A. Potebnya, in relation to the word, distinguished two types of

meaning, which he called “nearest” and “further”. The “nearest” meaning of the word corresponds to that part of its content, which he called the linguistic content, in other words, the information that all native speakers of the same language associate with this word. The “further” meaning of the word corresponds to that part of its content, which A. A. Potebnya called “extra-linguistic” or, as it is now customary to say, extralinguistic content, since his knowledge is not included in the knowledge of the language [4]. The meaning of the word is encyclopedic in its essence [5]. To characterize it, certain background information is necessary, which can be considered as a structure of generally accepted and to certain extent generalized knowledge, which is included in the general the system of culturally significant experience of native speakers. Thus, it can be argued that the meanings of words are correlated with cognitive structures or, in other words, blocks of knowledge that stand behind these meanings and provide their understanding. At the same time, it should be borne in mind that a person receives knowledge not only through purposeful, theoretical knowledge, but also a simple, everyday (not always conscious) comprehension of the world in everyday life, through the acquisition of the simplest –bodily, sensory –visual, sensory-motor – experience in everyday interaction with the surrounding world.

A more complete description of the meaning of the word has become possible due to the emergence of a cognitive direction in linguistics, the purpose of which can be formulated as follows: through the comprehension of language to penetrate into the forms of different structures of knowledge and describe the dependencies existing between them and language. In this new formulation of the research goal associated with a new understanding of the problem of the relationship between language and consciousness, one can see the fundamental difference between the cognitive paradigm in linguistics and the traditional one [6].

Thus, the modern view of the phenomenon of knowledge and meaning is increasingly determined by the cognitive approach to the problems of language and semantics. At the center of the new approach to language are two interrelated problems: 1) structures of knowledge representation; 2) methods of conceptual organization of knowledge in the processes of understanding and constructing language messages [6].

One of the conceptual models, the analysis of which contributes to the solution of both problems, is lexical polysemy, defined as the ability of lexicon units to have several semantically interrelated meanings, which serve as a means of

nominating objectively different objects and phenomena and are differentiated in speech-thinking activity syntagmatically (using context) and paradigmatically (based on semasiological oppositions).

Analysis of polysemous words (their meanings and meanings) in different languages in order to identify their similarities and differences caused by the need to have information about their similarities and differences in order to prevent translation errors, overcome semantic interference resulting from discrepancies in the semantic structures of polysemous words in different languages. Polysemous words are a semantic universal. This is the result of the universal laws of the development of ambiguity. However, the manifestation of these laws in different languages is different.

Polysemy is a semasio – onomasiological category, which reflects both the universal properties of language and thinking, as well as idioethnic, national-linguistic features [7].

The mechanism of ambiguity resolves to a certain extent the contradiction between the boundlessness of the world and concrete experience, the infinity of cognition, on the one hand, and the limited possibilities of language, perception and memory, on the other. The ambiguity of linguistic units is an economical mnemonic tool, a generalized way of storing linguistic and encyclopedic information, a mechanism for conceptualizing knowledge.

The existence of a subtext becomes possible because the meaning expressed with the help of a sound sign can itself be a signal or a sign for another meaning arising by association with the first. In the semantic structure of a polysemous word, both the lexical meaning of the word and the meaning are combined. They represent two main stratifications of the semantics of the word, therefore, in the comparative and contrastive analysis of a polysemous word, two levels of analysis of the semantics of the word should be distinguished: the level of the structure of lexical meaning – the level of stable meanings accepted in this language collective and normatively fixed by dictionaries and their components, and the level of the semantic structure of the word, which, containing the structure of lexical meaning and its elements, is a higher-order education focused not so much on the subject itself, designated by the word, as on its conceptual perception within the national self-awareness or within a given discourse. Accordingly, we can talk, – writes V. N. Manakin, – about two main types of meanings of words: 1) as about mental (conceptual) formations within a given linguistic culture; and 2) as about the specific content that a word acquires in a particular context [8].

A comparative analysis of the meanings of words and their meanings in different languages shows that in many cases the direct meanings of words can coincide. However, in cases of the operation of the law of semantic openness of words, the meanings of words in different languages do not coincide, since in one language the semantic structure of a word can be presented in an expanded form, when each seme in the semantic structure of the word can be conditionally considered as a separate independent word, the structure of which includes other semes, the latter, as necessary, also it can be decomposed into components. In the “unpacked” form, the word accommodates a much larger number of semantic features than the most complete explanatory dictionaries can reflect. It is on this feature of the word that its semantic openness, variability and variability are based [8].

In the semantic structures of polysemous words, universal models of the cognitive apparatus peculiar to all people are realized: 1) propositional (they isolate elements from a situation, determine the connections between them); 2) metaphorical models (the transition of values from one domain to another); 3) metonymic models (part – whole) [9].

Thus, in this study, the concept of semantic structure of a word means not only the connections of different meanings of one word, but also everything that determines the structure of a separate meaning of a word. From this point of view, the components of the semantic structure of the word are: meaning as an expression of a concept; the internal form of the word, which can be a component of the meaning of the word or forms a representation accompanying the meaning; the associative potential of the meanings of the word, which from the potential becomes real in the figurative meanings of the word; modal shades of the meaning of the word; emotional coloring of the word, including stylistic coloring of the meaning of the word.

List of used literature:

1. Щерба, Л. В. Методика исследования и речевая деятельность [Текст] / Л. В. Щерба. – М. : Рус. яз., 2005. – 216 с.
2. Кобозева, И. М. Лингвистическая семантика [Текст] : учеб. для студентов вузов / И. М. Кобозева. – М. : Едиториал УРСС, 2007. – 350 с
3. Кибрик, А. Е. Очерки по общим и прикладным вопросам языкознания [Текст] : монография / А. Е. Кибрик. – М. : Изд-во Моск. ун-та, 1992. – 336 с.
4. Потебня, А. А. Из записок по русской грамматике [Текст] : в 4 т. / А. А. Потебня. – М. : Просвещение, 1958. – С. 57.

5. Болдырев, Н. Н. Концепт и значение слова [Текст] / Н. Н. Болдырев // Методологические проблемы когнитивной лингвистики : сб. науч. тр. – Воронеж, 1987. – С. 25-36.
6. Болдырев, Н. Н. Концептуальное пространство когнитивной лингвистики [Текст] / Н. Н. Болдырев // Вопросы когнитивной лингвистики. – 2004. – № 1. – С. 18-36.
7. Ольшанский, И. Г. Глубинные падежи и контекстная семантика [Текст] / И. Г. Ольшанский // Контекстная семантизация лингвистических единиц : сб. науч. тр. – М., 1984. – Вып. 238. – С. 166.
8. Манакин, В. Н. Сопоставительная лексикология [Текст] / В. Н. Манакин. – Киев. : Знания, 2004. – 327 с.
9. Гак, В. Г. Сопоставительная типология (на материале французского и русского языков) [Текст] / В. Г. Гак. – М. : Международные отношения, 1977. – 264 с.
10. Nabiyeu, A. I. (2022). The Influence of Valence on the Peculiarities of the use of Marked and Unmarked Adverbs. European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630), 16, 10-13.
11. Nabiyeu, A. I. (2022, February). THE IMPORTANCE OF LISTENING IN LEARNING ENGLISH. In E Conference Zone (Vol. 1, pp. 12-13).

